

Dielectric Polarisation Studies of Complexes of Aniline with Phenol or Substituted-phenols

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The formation of complexes between aniline and phenol and substituted-phenols brings about the change in the dielectric properties of the systems. These changes are used to evaluate the formation constant and the dipole moment of the complexes using Few and Smith dielectric polarisation method. The dipole moment values and hence the interaction moments of the adducts are calculated by proposing possible structures. Using these values the nature of the interaction is discussed.

THE formation of hydrogen bond between an electron donor and an electron acceptor provokes changes in the relative positions of the nuclei and the electron clouds of the partners. As a consequence, dipole moment of the complex (μ_{AB}) will no longer be equal to the vector sum of the dipole moments of the components, μ_A and μ_B . This change in the dipole moment of the hydrogen bonded complexes could be used as an effective tool to understand the nature of the complexes. Such attempts were made by several workers¹⁻⁴.

The present work is an attempt to study the nature of interactions in the O—H...N complexes phenol-aniline, *p*-cresol-aniline and *p*-chlorophenol-aniline using dielectric polarisation method⁵.

Experimental

The dielectric measurement was carried out using a WTW DMO1 dipolemeter at a frequency of 2 MHz. The refractive index measurements were taken on a Abbe's refractometer. The temperature of the solution in the cell and refractometer were maintained by the circulation of water at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The compounds used were of AnalaR grade and were purified as per standard procedures⁶. Carbon tetrachloride (E. Merck, GR) was used as the solvent.

Results

The polarisations at infinite dilution of the electron donor ($(P_{A\infty})_S$), and the electron acceptor ($(P_{B\infty})_S$), are determined in the solvent carbon tetrachloride (S) using the limiting polarisation method⁵. The mixed solvent (BS) is prepared with various concentration of aniline in carbon tetrachloride. For each concentration of the mixed solvent the polarisation of the electron donor at infinite dilution, $(P_{A\infty})_{BS}$, is determined and the results are given in Table 1.

The excess polarisation due to hydrogen bonding (ΔP) is defined as

$$\Delta P = (P_{AB\infty})_S - [(P_{A\infty})_S + (P_{B\infty})_S]$$

and is related to the equilibrium constant (K) as

$$\frac{1}{(P_{A\infty})_{BS} - (P_{A\infty})_S} = \frac{1}{K\Delta P} \frac{M_B}{W_B d_{BS}} + \frac{1}{\Delta P}$$

where, M_B is the molecular weight of B, d_{BS} the density of the mixed solvent BS, and W_B the weight fraction of the electron acceptor B in the mixed solvent.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF $(P_{A\infty})_{BS}$ WITH WEIGHT FRACTION OF ANILINE

eight fraction of aniline in mixed solvent $100 W_B$	Molar polarisation $(P_{A\infty})_{BS}$	$\frac{10^3}{(P_{A\infty})_{BS} - (P_{A\infty})_S}$	$\frac{M_B \times 10^{-3}}{W_B d_{BS}}$
Phenol-aniline			
1.817	84.0	19.2	3.3
3.027	86.7	12.7	2.0
4.987	90.4	8.6	1.2
6.283	92.3	7.4	1.0
7.461	93.8	6.7	0.8
<i>p</i>-Cresol-aniline			
0.681	90.1	45.5	8.7
1.814	92.5	21.7	3.3
3.432	94.6	14.9	1.8
4.909	96.1	12.2	1.2
6.511	97.0	11.0	0.9
<i>p</i>-Chlorophenol-aniline			
0.600	160	3.2	9.8
0.986	166	2.4	6.0
1.849	182	1.7	3.2
3.043	194	1.4	2.0
5.078	203	1.3	1.2

Graphs were drawn between

$$\frac{1}{(P_{A\infty})_{BS} - (P_{A\infty})_S} \text{ and } \frac{M_B}{W_B d_{BS}} \text{ (Fig. 1)}$$

to evaluate ΔP and K for all the systems studied.

Fig. 1 Plots of $\frac{1}{(P_{AB})_{BS} - (P_{AB})_S}$ vs $\frac{M_B}{W_B d_{BS}}$: (a) phenol-aniline, (b) *p*-cresol-aniline and (c) *p*-chlorophenol-aniline systems.

The slope of the straight line gives the value of $1/K\Delta P$, while the intercept on the Y-axis gives $1/\Delta P$ from which K and ΔP are calculated. The dipole moment of the complex formed is given by

$$\mu_{AB} = 0.01281 \{[(P_{AB})_S - R_D]T\}^{1/2}$$

where, R_D is the molar refraction and T the absolute temperature. The observed μ_{AB} values are given in Table 4 along with K values.

Discussion

The dipole moment of the complexes determined gives information about the dipole alignment and hence can be used to elucidate the specific geometric structures of the hydrogen bonded complexes. The values of μ (dipole moment) and θ (angle between dipole vector and hydrogen bond axis) have been calculated for all the components studied (Table 2). Theoretically, the dipole moment for the possible *cis*- and *trans*-forms of the complexes are calculated by the vectorial addition of the components μ_A and μ_B and are given in Table 3.

TABLE 2—DIPOLE MOMENT OF COMPONENTS

Component	Dipole moment μ (D)	Angle θ^a
Phenol	1.59	25°
<i>p</i> -Cresol	1.66	38°26'
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	2.13	20°44'
Aniline	1.58	61°26'

TABLE 3—DIPOLE MOMENT OF 1 : 1 COMPLEX

System	Calculated μ_{AB} for	
	<i>trans</i> -Form (D)	<i>cis</i> -Form (D)
Aniline + Phenol	3.01	2.31
<i>p</i> -Cresol	3.17	2.09
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	2.82	3.48

Schuster⁷ with LCAO-MO studies of the hydrogen bonding showed that in structures with same orientation of the functional group forming the hydrogen bond, the arrangement with the smallest dipole moment has the lower energy and will be more stable. The most stable configuration of the

Fig. 2. Structure of phenol-aniline complexes.

1:1 complexes studied for which the potential energy is minimum are shown in Fig. 2. The *cis*-form of the complex shows lowest dipole moment in the case of phenol and *p*-cresol whereas the *trans*-form gives the lowest moment in the case of *p*-chlorophenol complex. The CH₃ substitution in the *para*-position of phenol slightly affects the dipole moment of phenol whereas the substitution of Cl, which is highly electronegative in nature, changes the direction of the dipole moment considerably (Fig. 2). This may be the reason for the lowest dipole moment in *trans*-form of the complex in the case of *p*-chlorophenol-aniline system.

Assuming the interaction moment has the direction of the hydrogen bond itself⁹, the magnitude of $\Delta\mu$ can be calculated for a complex of moment μ_{AB} between an electron donor of moment μ_A and an electron acceptor of moment μ_B from the relation,

$$\Delta\mu = [\mu_{AB}^2 - (\mu_A \sin \theta_A - \mu_B \sin \theta_B)^2]^{1/2} - \mu_A \cos \theta_A - \mu_B \cos \theta_B$$

The $\Delta\mu$ values for all the systems studied have been calculated (Table 4) along with other parameters.

TABLE 4—VARIOUS PARAMETERS OBTAINED FOR COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Parameter	Phenol + aniline	<i>p</i> -Cresol + aniline	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol + aniline
1.	Effective molecular polarisation ($P_{AB\omega}^2$) _s	197.76	180.72	306.74
2.	Induced polarisation (ΔP)	38.46	12.12	102.04
3.	Equilibrium constant (K)	0.55	1.52	4.23
4.	Effective dipole moment (μ_{AB})	2.90	2.75	3.70
5.	Interaction moment ($\Delta\mu$)	0.61 (<i>cis</i>)	0.67 (<i>cis</i>)	0.90 (<i>trans</i>)

The interaction moment $\Delta\mu$, which represents the redistribution of charge along the O—H—N axis, may arise due to classical electrostatic effects and due to delocalisation effects. Mere electrostatic effect does not contribute appreciably to the dipole moment of the complex. The induced dipole moment due to polarisation as calculated by Ratajczak⁹, by Frank method, are found to be of the order 0.15 to 0.2 D for the systems studied. The $\Delta\mu$ values obtained in the systems studied are higher than the induced dipole moment values. The polarisation effect causes a significant change in charge redistribution and hence to the dipole moment. The delocalisation effect due to the formation of hydrogen bond in the present systems does not seem to be of simple polarisation effect alone and it is reasonable to expect intermolecular charge redistribution leading to charge transfer which results in the enhancement of dipole moment.

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